

Force Analysis of Tractor Beam Magnetic System

Jayaram A. S.

Associate Professor (Retd), Dr Ambedkar Institute of Technology,
Bangalore, India

Abstract

This paper presents a two-dimensional force analysis of a tractor beam magnetic system using a simplified arrangement of four magnets. The equilibrium position and the direction of resultant forces around the equilibrium point are experimentally and mathematically analysed. The study also shows that the equilibrium distance is independent of the strength of the test magnet.

1 Introduction

The tractor beam magnet experiments are relatively new and emerged around 2015. Many attempts have been made toward the analysis of forces in both three-dimensional and two-dimensional systems[1],[2].

In 2022, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) published a research demonstration showing the use of a magnetic tractor beam to steer a catheter over a distance of 100 mm with high precision[3],[4]

This paper shows that, around the equilibrium position, the vector resultants are almost directed toward the equilibrium point.

It is also observed that the magnets nearest to the test magnet (the two small magnets) contribute most of the force, while the remaining surrounding magnets are not essential for the basic analysis.

Hence, in this experimental study, only one larger magnet and two smaller magnets are used along with the test magnet.

2 Experimental Arrangement

Figure 1: Experimental arrangement

This paper presents a detailed two-dimensional analysis of the tractor beam magnetic arrangement. It also shows that a full three-dimensional analysis is not necessary at the basic level.

The paper highlights that the equilibrium distance does not depend upon the strength of the test magnet, provided the size of the test magnet is not excessively large.

The paper also shows that the vector forces around the equilibrium position are almost exactly directed toward the equilibrium point.

3 Sizes and positions of Magnets

Figure 2: Sizes of magnets

The experimental setup includes:

- A central magnet of 25 mm diameter and 5 mm height
- Two small magnets of 5 mm diameter and 5 mm height
- A test magnet of 5 mm diameter and 5 mm height

The two small magnets are placed at an angle of 48° apart. Their poles are opposite to that of the central magnet.

The test magnet also has the same pole orientation as the two small magnets. All magnets used are NdFeB permanent magnets.

4 Arrangement of Magnetic Poles

Figure 3: Magnetic poles

The central large magnet has its north pole facing upward, while all the small magnets, including the test magnet, have their south poles facing upward.

5 The Experiment

Figure 4: Effective forces

The magnets nearest to the test magnet (the two small magnets) contribute most significantly to the force acting on the test magnet.

The remaining surrounding magnets are therefore neglected in this simplified analysis. The small test magnet remains in equilibrium due to:

- Repulsive forces from the two small magnets
- Attractive force from the large central magnet

The arrangement is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Forces on test magnet

The small magnets are fixed to the large magnet using adhesive tape such that the angle between them is maintained at 48° .

6 Calculations

The experimental results show that the equilibrium position is approximately 25 mm from the center of the large magnet.

For this position, the calculations are carried out as shown in the figures.

Figure 6: Force calculations

The attractive force F_a between the large magnet and the test magnet is calculated first.

The repulsive forces between the test magnet and magnets m_1 and m_2 are denoted by f_1 and f_2 respectively.

The resultant repulsive force F_r due to f_1 and f_2 is then calculated.

Let:

- M = strength of the large magnet
- m_1 and m_2 = strengths of the smaller magnets
- m_t = strength of the test magnet

Note: In the equations, the test magnet is denoted by m_t .

The standard equation for the force between short magnets placed side by side is: (Note :The equations are based on the short magnetic dipole approximation.)

$$F_a = \frac{3\mu_0 M m_t}{4\pi r^4} \quad (1)$$

where,

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ H/m}$$

Substituting,

$$F_a = \frac{3M m_t \times 10^{-7}}{r^4} \quad (2)$$

For r in mm, the above equation must be multiplied by 10^{12} .

Hence,

$$F_a = \frac{3M m_t \times 10^5}{r^4} \quad (3)$$

The above equation gives the attractive force between the large magnet and the test magnet.

The repulsive forces between m_1 and m_t , and between m_2 and m_t , are equal in magnitude and act at angles of 28.3° above and below the x-axis respectively.

Hence, the resultant repulsive force is:

$$F_r = 2f_1 \cos(28.3^\circ) \quad (4)$$

Using the same force equation for f_1 :

$$f_1 = f_2 = \frac{3 \times 10^5 \times m_1 \times m_t}{r_1^4} \quad (5)$$

Substituting into Equation (4):

$$F_r = 2 \times \frac{3 \times 10^5 \times m_1 \times m_t \times \cos(28.3^\circ)}{r_1^4} \quad (6)$$

Simplifying,

$$F_r = \frac{5.28 \times 10^5 \times m_1 \times m_t}{r_1^4} \quad (7)$$

At equilibrium,

$$F_a = F_r$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{3 \times 10^5 \times M \times m_t}{r^4} = \frac{5.28 \times 10^5 \times m_1 \times m_t}{r_1^4} \quad (8)$$

From Equation (8), it can be seen that the strength of the test magnet m_t has no effect on the equilibrium distance, since it cancels out.

Thus,

$$\frac{3M}{r^4} = \frac{5.28m_1}{r_1^4} \quad (9)$$

Rearranging,

$$\frac{M}{m_1} = \frac{5.28r^4}{3r_1^4} \quad (10)$$

From the experiment:

$$r = 25 \text{ mm}$$

and

$$r_1 = 12.8 \text{ mm}$$

Substituting these values gives:

$$\frac{M}{m_1} \approx 26.5 \quad (11)$$

Note: This is the ratio of the strength of the large magnet to that of the small magnet.

This ratio is used in subsequent force calculations.

7 Test Magnet Strength -Experimental Verification

Equation (8) shows that the strength of the test magnet has no effect on the equilibrium position.

This was experimentally verified by placing a tiny magnet along with the test magnet, as shown in the figure.

Figure 7: size of test magnet

It was observed that the equilibrium position still remained approximately 25 mm, confirming that the strength of the test magnet has negligible effect on the equilibrium distance.

8 Finding Forces Around the Test Point “P”

Figure 8: Forces around the test point

The points “a”, “b”, ... “f” shown in the figure are considered for force analysis.

The force at any point, say point “A”, is calculated by finding the distances of the test magnet from magnets m_1 , m_2 , and the large magnet M .

At point “A”, the distances from m_1 and m_2 are different.

Figure 9: Distances at test point "A"

Hence, the forces f_1 and f_2 are also different.

Here,

$$r_a = 28.2 \text{ mm}$$

Also, the strength of the test magnet is taken as:

$$m_t = 1$$

since only force ratios are considered.
From Equation (11),

$$M = 26.5$$

Substituting these values into Equation (3):

$$F_a = \frac{3 \times 26.5 \times 10^5}{28.2^4} \quad (12)$$

This gives:

$$F_a = 12.6 \text{ units}$$

Similarly,

$$f_1 = 3.7 \text{ units}$$

and

$$f_2 = 6.6 \text{ units}$$

At all positions, the values of F_a , f_1 , f_2 , and resultant force F_r are calculated and tabulated in Table 1.

Test points	Net resultant force	Angle (in degrees)
a	5.42	216
b	2.9	180
c	5.42	144
d	31.8	75
e	10.1	0
f	31.8	285
p	0	0

Figure 10: Table showing results

The resultant force directions at different points are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Force vectors

An enlarged view is provided in Figure 12 for better visualization of the force directions.

Figure 12: Force trajectory at points

- Due to symmetry about the x-axis, the vector at point “c” is the mirror image of the vector at point “a”.

Similarly, the vector at point “d” is the mirror image of that at point “f”.

- The magnitude of the resultant force at a farther point such as “a” is smaller than that at a nearer point such as “d”.

This is because all magnetic forces decrease with increasing distance.

- It is interesting to note that the force vector at point “f” is not directed toward the equilibrium point “P”, but away from it.

This occurs because the repulsive force from the nearby magnet m_1 dominates over the other forces.

It was calculated that, as the test magnet moves closer to the equilibrium point, the vector direction gradually changes toward the equilibrium point, as shown by the dotted purple curve.

At farther points such as “a”, the vector direction is almost, though not exactly, toward the equilibrium point.

9 Conclusion

1. A tractor beam arrangement can be realized using only four magnets.
2. The equilibrium distance is independent of the strength of the test magnet.
3. Most force vectors around the equilibrium point are approximately directed toward the equilibrium position, indicating quasi-restoring behaviour.
4. As the test point moves farther from the equilibrium position, the magnitude of the resultant force decreases.

References

- [1] Cheedket, S. and Sirisathitkul, C. “Comparison of Closed-form Solutions to Experimental Magnetic Force Between Two Cylindrical Magnets.” *EUREKA: Physics and Engineering*, no. 4, pp. 141–146, 2021.
- [2] Adams, Michael P. “Understanding Two Dimensional Tractor Magnets: Theory and Realizations.” *American Journal of Physics*, vol. 92, no. 8, pp. 576–582, 2024.
- [3] C. Limpabandhu and Z. T. H. Tse, “Exploring Magnetic Tractor Beam Technology for Enhanced Catheter Steering: Insights From Simulation and Experimentation,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 125871–125880, 2024.
- [4] Limpabandhu, Chayabhan. “Magnetically Actuated Device using Magnetic Tractor Beam Coupling for Medical Interventions.” PhD dissertation, Queen Mary University of London, 2024.